

Benzotriazolium Salts: Emergent Readily Accessible Bench-stable Lewis Acid Catalysts

Tobias Danelzik,^a Sumi Joseph,^a Christian Mück-Lichtenfeld,^a Constantin G. Daniliuc,^a and Olga García Mancheño^{*a}

Organic Chemistry Institute, Westfälische Wilhelms University Münster, Corrensstraße 36, 48149 Münster.

Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: In this work, benzotriazolium salts have been introduced as efficient, readily accessible, bench-stable Lewis acid catalysts. Though these sorts of *N*-heterocyclic compounds have found wide applications as ionic liquids or electrolytes, their Lewis acid catalytic activity remained unexplored. Herein, their potential as Lewis acid catalysts was demonstrated in two prototypical allylic and Nazarov cyclization reactions, showing a matching reactivity and allowing low catalytic loadings (down to 0.5 mol%).

The ability of Lewis acids (LA) to form acid-base adducts and activate small molecules has been widely used in synthesis and catalysis,¹ being hence established as a powerful tool in a large variety of chemical processes. Although classical main-group Lewis acids containing elements with low-lying free orbitals like boron, aluminum, silicon or phosphorus have been studied intensively,^{1,2} nitrogen centered Lewis-acids have just recently evoked a rising interest. This field was most probably long neglected, since the common compounds showing a N-centered electrophilic behavior, such as nitrenes, azides or diazo-derivatives, lead to rather unstable Lewis acid-Lewis base adducts, or present strong oxidizing properties like nitronium salts, hampering their application as Lewis acids.³ Alternatively, the carbene-isoelectronic cationic nitrenium ions have proved more suitable for the design of novel nitrogen Lewis acid structures. Hence, since the group of Boche presented the first stable nitrenium ions by methylation of triazoles in 1996,⁴ this type of salts became important building blocks for the synthesis of organocatalysts, serving as precatalysts,⁵ dual catalysis,⁶ or ligands.⁷ Nevertheless, the first example of a stable adduct formation between triazinium ions and several Lewis bases was just reported by Gandelman *et al.* in 2017 (Scheme 1A, left),⁸ which resembled the Lewis acidic behavior that was already known for their heavier phosphonium^{9,10} and arsenium¹¹ analogues. This Lewis acid reactivity was then further demonstrated by the group of Stephan using indazolium salts (Scheme

1A, middle),¹² as well as extended to frustrated Lewis pair (FLP)¹³ driven chemistry (Scheme 1A, right).¹⁴

Scheme 1. A. Nitrenium-based LA structures employed in acid-base adduct formation and FLP chemistry. B. First nitrenium LA catalysis. C. Benzotriazolium salts (BZT) as novel LA catalysts.

Furthermore, only very recently the unprecedented use of nitrenium-based Lewis acids in catalysis has been described. Thus, in 2020 Goicoechea *et al.* employed catalytic amounts of a triazinium cation for promoting several organic reactions, including hydrogenations, reductions and a Friedel-Crafts reaction (Scheme 1B).¹⁵ However, in this pioneer report only six-membered triaziniums have been proven efficient N-based Lewis acids and a few limited types of reactions involving mainly carbonyl and silane activation could be accomplished to date. Therefore, the development of further nitrenium-based catalysts with enhanced and/or adjusted Lewis acid properties to allow for a broader synthetic application is still highly desirable.

Inspired by the state-of-the-art and encouraged to solve some of the current reactivity limitations, we envisioned benzotriazolium salts, which are widely used as ionic liquids (IL), electrolytes or fluids,¹⁶ as suitable new platforms to provide alternative potent N-based Lewis acid catalyst structures. Despite of their ready accessibility and easy modulability that make them excellent candidates to this purpose, their catalytic activity as Lewis acids remained unexplored.¹⁷ We herein present the first example of benzotriazolium-based Lewis acids as efficient, bench-stable catalysts for two benchmark reactions implying a carbonyl and hydroxyl group activation, such as allylic and Nazarov cyclizations towards synthetically valuable chromenes and cyclopentenones, respectively (Scheme 1C).

We started our investigation by preparing a series of 1-methyl-3-methyl (**1a-d**), 3-(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl) (**1e-f**) and 3-aryl (**1g-i**) triazolium salts with different counteranions upon methylation of the corresponding benzotriazole with MeOTf or Me₃OBF₄, followed, when needed, by a subsequent counteranion exchange (Figure 1A, see S.I. for details). Alternatively, the iodide salt was also prepared by reaction with MeI, which anion was later on exchanged to BF₄⁻ and a BAR^F-type anion with AgBF₄ and NaBAR^F₄ or Na/KB(C₆F₅)₄, respectively. Similarly, various methoxytriazolium **2a-d** and previously reported triaziniums **3a-c**^{8,15} were also synthesized.

Figure 1. A. Synthesis of benzotriazolium salts **1-2** and **B.** X-ray structures of representative derivatives **1a-d** (ellipsoid contours given at the 50% probability level).

To evaluate the relative Lewis acidity of the triazolium salts, the Gutmann-Beckett test (GBT)¹⁸ was then performed in acetone-d₆ and the Acceptor-Number (AN) was calculated (see Table S1 in the S.I.), revealing an apparent moderate Lewis acidity (≤ 20 AN).¹⁹ Additionally the global electrophilicity index (GEI) and fluoride ion affinity were calculated for a series of 1,3-dimethyl benzotriazoles (**1a**, **1b**, and **1d**) with their corresponding counteranion at DFT level of theory, supporting the postulation of a negligible influence of the anion to the Lewis-acidity (see S.I. for details). Hence, the exchange of BF₄⁻ with Na or K[B(C₆F₅)₄] and NaBAR^F₄ to bulkier counteranions resulted in a counterintuitively slight decrease of Lewis acidity. Moreover, the analysis of the X-ray structures of the benzotriazolium series **1a-d**²⁰ revealed the expected increasing benzotriazole-anion distance trend upon increasing of the bulkiness of the anion from OTf⁻ to the less coordinative barfates (Figure 1B, see S.I. for details).

Next, we focused on the evaluation of their reactivity towards cyclization reactions. We chose the allylic cyclization upon the activation of the alcohol **4a** to form 2*H*-chromene (**5a**)²¹ in THF as benchmark reaction to test the ability of benzotriazolium salts to act as Lewis acid catalysts (Scheme 2). This cyclization did not proceed in the absence of a Lewis acid, even at elevated temperatures (70 °C).

Scheme 2. Catalyst screening for the allyl cyclization reaction of **4a**.^a

^a Conditions: **4a** (0.2 mmol), LA catalyst (10 mol%) in THF (0.1 M) for 18 h at 70 °C under Ar. Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using CH₂Br₂ as internal standard. n.d. = not detected. (See S.I. for full optimization).

^b Same yield for LA catalyst obtained from methylation with Me₃OBF₄ and exchange from I with AgBF₄, respectively. ^c Reaction performed under air.

The nitrenium series were then tested using a 10 mol% of catalytic loading under argon atmosphere. Dismissed yields or decomposition were generally observed for most of the Lewis acid catalysts **1-3**, as well as for the strong Lewis acid BF₃•Et₂O. Gratifyingly, the LA catalysts **1b**, **2b** and **3c** performed well in this benchmark reaction, showing up to 77% yield with catalyst **1b**. This result could not be improved by changing the

temperature or solvent, which both caused a decrease in yield (see S.I.). Moreover, the presence of oxygen led to a detriment of the yield, providing the product **5a** in only 33% when the reaction was run under air with **1b**, most probably due to partial oxidation/aromatization of the product.

To confirm that the catalytic activation is induced by our triazolium species, we carried out some control experiments. Since this kind of reaction can also be promoted by strong Brønsted acids that might be formed in the media, we tested our system in presence of 1 mol% of triflic acid or the Brookhart's-type acid $[\text{H}(\text{OEt}_2)_2]^+[\text{B}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_4]^-$ as catalyst at both 70 °C and r.t., but only decomposition could be detected (see S.I., Table S6 for more details). This is in line with the observed beneficial moderate Lewis acidity to avoid decomposition, while allowing for an efficient promotion this cyclization reaction. Moreover, we were able to reproduce the good results with **1b** obtained through a different synthetic approach by I⁻-anion exchange using AgBF_4 instead of direct dimethylation with excess of Me_3OBF_4 to rule out any traces of HBF_4 or Me_3OBF_4 . Furthermore, we used NaBF_4 in catalytic amounts to exclude any influence of the counteranion on the activation process of this reaction. As expected, the ring closure did not proceed, proving that the triazolium cation is indeed inducing the ring closure. With the optimized conditions in hand, the scope of the allylic cyclization was next explored (Scheme 3). First of all, it is worthy to note that the reaction could be scaled up to 1 mmol without any significant detriment on the yield (65% vs. 77%). Moreover, the formation of the products bearing different substitution patterns was pleasantly observed in every case. The methyl substitution at both the aryl and allylic moiety of the substrate gave the desired products **5b-d** in moderate to good yields (53-76%), while the π -extended compound **5e** showed a high stability leading to a good 88% isolated yield. Moreover, strong electron donating groups such as methoxy were well tolerated, providing 6- and 5-substituted chromenes **5f** and **5g** in 83% and 53% yield, respectively. Finally, less reactive substrates bearing electron withdrawing groups such as halogen or nitro substituents could also be enrolled in the reaction, providing chromenes **5h-j** in moderate yields (30-50%).²³

Scheme 3. Scope of the allylic cyclization to 2*H*-chromenes **4**. Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using CH_2Br_2 as internal standard. Isolated yield given in brackets. ^a 1.0 mmol scale.

Due to the already known nitrenium activation of carbonyl groups for deoxygenation reactions (see Scheme 1B), we decided to further investigate the nitrenium series **1-3** in the

Nazarov cyclization. This reaction is known to be activated by either LA metal-based catalysts²⁴ or phosphonium cations,¹⁰ and represents one of the most versatile methods for the synthesis of natural products and bioactive molecules containing cyclopentenone moieties.²⁵ In particular, we chose dienone **6a** as model substrate²⁶ for determining the activity and requirements of the Lewis acid nitrenium salts (Table 1).

Table 1. Catalyst screening in the model Nazarov cyclization of **6**.^a

Entry	LA catalyst (mol%)	Yield 7a (%) ^b
1	1b (1)	47
2	1c (1)	30
3	1d (1)	99(86) ^d
4	2d (1)	15
5	3a (1)	7
6	1d (1)	(77) ^{d,e}
7	1d (5)	>99
8	1d (0.5)	69 ^f

^a Conditions: **4** (0.2 mmol) and LA catalyst in CH_2Cl_2 (0.1 M) at r.t. for 24 h under Ar. ^b Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using CH_2Br_2 as internal standard. ^c >20:1 d.r. determined by ¹H-NMR for all catalytic reactions. ^d Isolated yield in brackets. ^e Reaction performed under air. ^f 0.4 mmol scale reaction.

Aiming at identifying highly efficient catalyst structures, 1 mol% of the salts **1-3** was initially employed at room temperature in CH_2Cl_2 as standard conditions. To our delight, LA catalysts **1b-d**, **2d** and **3a** were able to promote the cyclization ranking from 7 to 99% conversion (entries 1-5), whereas the other nitrenium salts, including the already established triazinium catalyst **3c**, showed no catalytic activity in this reaction (see S.I for full screening). However, there was not a perfect correlation between the LA strength and yield of the cyclopentenone **7**. Thus, catalyst **1d** with a slightly lower LA strength than the other catalysts led to full conversion and an excellent 86% isolated yield (entry 3). Moreover, performing this reaction under air instead of inert atmosphere resulted in an insignificant drop of yield, which also shows the excellent bench, moisture and air stability of this catalyst (entry 6). Additionally, while increasing the amount of catalyst to 5 mol% resulted in a similar nearly quantitative yield (entry 7). The remarkable performance of triazolium **1d** allowed the activation of the dienone system **6a** even at a 0.5 mol% loading to provide **7a** in a good 69% yield (entry 8).

These results encouraged us to further investigate the relative kinetics and potency of our catalytic system by monitoring the reaction with selected nitrenium LAs by ¹H NMR (Figure 2; shown 3 h, see S.I. for 15 h monitoring). To this purpose, we chose a 5 mol% of catalyst loading due to the low conversion

for most of the studied nitrenium salts during the catalyst screening with 1 mol%. The highly activating triazolium **1d** showed full conversion after only 1 h. Due to this rapid evolution, the reaction with 1 mol% of **1d** was also investigated, in which a good 70% yield could be still observed after 3 h. As expected, for the less activating triazinium **3a** or catalysts **1b** and **2d** a low linear conversion with less than 20% or 10% yield after 3 h was observed. Moreover, the control experiments with $\text{Na}[\text{B}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_4]$ and **1a** showed no catalytic activity at all.

Figure 2. Kinetic experiment with an exemplary choice of catalysts **1-3** (5 mol%) in the Nazarov cyclization (see S.I. for full study).

Lastly, the scope and limitations of the Nazarov cyclization were explored (Scheme 4). The upscaling of the standard reaction to 1 mmol using 1 mol% of the Lewis acid catalyst **1d** was first performed, showing the robustness of the method by providing a similar 75% yield. A different substitution on the ester moiety was well-tolerated (Me, **7b** and *t*Bu, **7c**), in which *tert*-butyl led to the best result with a 98% yield on the product **7c**. Furthermore, the different substitution on the R^2 group was also investigated. While the less reactive dienones bearing neutral Ph or weak activating *p*-tolyl rests (products: **7d**, 81%; **7e**, 62%) or electron deficient aryl groups (product **7f**, 46%) required 5 mol% of the catalyst to provide synthetically useful conversions, electron rich systems such as 3,4,5-triMeOPh provided the corresponding product **7g** in almost quantitative yield.

In summary, we have introduced benzotriazolium salts as a new class of bench-stable and efficient N-centered Lewis-acid catalysts. The new structures were benchmarked with already known nitrenium Lewis acids such as triazinium cations, showing a remarkable higher activity in the studied allylic cyclization and Nazarov reactions, implying a hydroxyl and carbonyl activation, respectively. Moreover, kinetic reaction monitoring of the Nazarov cyclization demonstrated the high reactivity of these N-based Lewis acid structures, which was confirmed by the low 1 mol% catalyst loading required, and shows already their potential for a wide-ranging field of applications in Lewis acid catalysis.

Scheme 4. Scope of the Nazarov cyclization. Yields of the isolated products are given. ^a Results with 5 mol% of **1c** in brackets.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

Complete reaction screening, experimental procedures, characterization data, additional experiments, x-ray structure analysis of catalysts **1a-d**, **1f**, **1i** and **2a-d**, and NMR spectra of isolated compounds (PDF).

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

* E-mail: olga.garcia@uni-muenster.de

Author Contributions

All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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